

FUNDING EDUCATION AND EDUCATIONAL ADMINISTRATION IN THE FACE OF RISING INFLATION AND EMERGING TRENDS IN 21ST CENTURY NIGERIA.

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Abstract: Every striving human action and endeavor requires funding to motivate its continuity. Funding education is a crucial element of a successful educational system. Education Funding refers to financial support provided to students for their education. Both private and government agencies provide funds appropriated for long-term and short-term purposes. The Federal Republic of Nigeria's policy of free education at all levels, as stated in the FRN national policy (2013) session eight, is sponsored through financial support and assistance from International and Local Development Partners, grants for research, and other donor agencies. However, Education is a capital-intensive social service that requires a strong financial base to succeed. Therefore, financing educational administration should not be treated with levity, if educational goals and objectives must be achieved. In line with this, educational administrators must also be conscious of the rising inflation and other trends that have been newly created or noticed in education growth and development and be prudent in managing the scarce resources allotted to education.

The funding undulations in the major revenue item of education in this era mean that without careful planning and rationalization of educational expenditure, the implementation of education programs and projects would be subject to frequent disruptions and distortions. Arising from these axioms, this article explores funding educational administration in the face of rising inflation and emerging trends in 21st-century Nigeria.

Keywords: Education, Education Funding, Education Administration, and Emerging Trends

INTRODUCTION.

Education funding, fund management, and management of emerging trending issues in education by educational administrators has been an issue of discussion, as it has made education and the achievement of its aims and objectives almost an illusion in the face of rising inflation in Nigeria. Education funding from the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisations UNESCO (Last update: 27 July 2023) View, is a political and social decision-making process through which public revenues and other resources are collected and allocated to finance education and lifelong learning opportunities. It is concerned with translating public and governmental visions and goals for education and lifelong learning into financing sources, amounts, and ways of financing

schools and educational institutions. Financing involves governance, public sector systems, legal frameworks, policies, mechanisms, and administrative structures. It also requires governments to regulate, distribute, and allocate those resources, for example, directly to schools and educational institutions, sub-regional governments or authorities, levels, and types of education. Moreover, the distribution of these resources to different geographical areas, specific populations, or groups profoundly affects the equality of educational opportunities. To this extent, Ken Robinson, an education enthusiast, noted that the role of education administrator or leadership is not and should not be command and control, the real role of education leadership is climate control, creating a climate of possibility. In line with this, it is the responsibility of the school administrator to

- Provide a school budget and appropriate school funds.
- Keep records of appropriated funds for accountability.
- Promote total obedience and compliance with school policies, laws and regulations.
- Advance and roll out educational programmes
- Employ, educate, and motivate staff
- Advise students when required
- Determine conflicts and other emerging issues.
- Support in the development of the school curriculum

The education system is structured to function with human and material resources. The function of the internal administration of a school is to ensure the implementation of policies and coordinate, supervise, and organise the human and material resources of the school to accomplish the overall aims and objectives. The achievement of these objectives requires adequate human and material resources. Whereas human resources include teaching and non-teaching staff, which could also be referred to as academic and non-academic staff, materials resources are the infrastructural facilities in the school such as administrative blocks, offices, ICT facilities, libraries, laboratories, portable water, electricity, internet services, classrooms, etc. The availability of these instructional materials will promote a better school climate that will enhance the teaching and learning atmosphere. These resources cannot come without funds for procurement and maintenance. The funds required for school administration are usually large, due to the undulating education funding and inflation in Nigeria, schools are to a large extent beginning to lose their original status. Educational administrators are expected to be financially prudent, avoiding wastage through a better accountability process.

Conceptual Review:

Education, funding, and administration are the basic elements of this article. Therefore, the conceptual reviews were anchored on them, reflecting on their importance in achieving the overall aims and objectives of education in Nigeria.

Education.

Education is considered a purposeful endeavour to enhance individual values and knowledge, making the individual a better person. In society, people are born into different cultural backgrounds, norms, and values that

inform and direct their behavioural patterns. These elements are what bind them together. In the bid to coexist peacefully, from generation to generation, society must develop a mechanism and system of transferring these cultural elements to the younger generation. This system and mechanism applied by society to transfer their cultural norms and values to their younger generation is what is referred to as education.

To this extent, Rousseau opined that the "Education of man commenced at birth before he could speak and understand what he was already instructed. Experience is the forerunner of precept. In line with this, Aristotle re-echoed it when he asserted that" Education is the creation of a sound mind in a sound body. It develops men's faculty, especially his mind, so that he may be able to enjoy the implementation of Supreme Court goodness and beauty, of which perfect happiness essentially consists. Therefore, it is pertinent to state that for harmonious coexistence in society to occur, men need to understand things around their environment, and understanding them perfectly requires the instruction and mentorship of knowledgeable persons to share common experiences with members of society and pass from one generation to the next through education.

The education concept concerns what is important to learn and how individuals should acquire such learning.

Education is an effective and efficient means of shaping individuals' and society's future world. Its actions are significant, in creating and communicating knowledge, skills, and values to society. Colleges and universities prepare professionals who develop, lead, manage, teach, work in, and influence societies and communities. Society development depends on the products of educated minds, inventions, innovations, and adaptation imparted by education to individuals and society.

In the past, the Nigerian government treated education with all seriousness, which is why, in its constitution, it was clearly stated that education should:

- Develop the individual into a morally sound, patriotic, and effective citizen;
- Imbibe worthwhile values to the child;
- Build a morally sound and useful society.
- Integrate the individuals into the immediate community, Nigerian society, and the world:
- Provide equal access to qualitative educational opportunities for all citizens at all educational levels, within and outside the formal school system:

Inculcate national consciousness, values, and national unity and develop appropriate mental, physical, social, and competent abilities for individuals to live in and contribute positively to society. Other specific goals of education as specified in the constitution include

- Ensuring and sustaining unfettered access to equity education for the total development of the individual;
- Ensuring quality of education delivery at all levels;
- Promoting functional education for skill acquisition. job creation and poverty reduction;
- Ensuring periodic review, effectiveness and relevance of the curriculum at all levels to meet the needs of society and the world at large.

- Collaborating with development partners, the private sector, Non-Governmental Organisations and local communities to support and fund education; and
- Promoting information technology capability at all levels.

Generally, the education goal in Nigeria is to transform individuals and society from un-civilised to a civilised and well-developed state.

Having anchored this article to this extent, it is of note that, for effective and efficient actualization of this project, it is pertinent for a proficient, prolific, and prudent person to administer and manage all education programs, activities, and even funds provided to process the procurement of essential material resources and to staff the process. Subsequently, education funding shall be discussed briefly here in this write-up.

Education Funding;

Education funding is a term used to describe financial and in-kind educational resources available to education. Education funding addresses how resources are allocated, used, and accounted for, to achieve sustainable and quality education for all children in the country.

Nwanguma and Dede (2024) opined that Education financing is a major area in Nigeria where politics has a great influence, especially in public schools where budget allocation is determined according to the political interest of the politicians. There has been a debate among elites as to whether the government alone should fund education, some argued that the cost of education should be borne essentially by parents with the government providing the enabling environment. They posited that families and individuals ought to pay fees to access available public education services: - otherwise, these services would not be available or their quality would become unacceptably low. This largely means that those whose parents are poor will not be able to pay for and access educational services. In divergence, others opined, that education should not only be free but also compulsory as it is a right of the citizens that must be funded fully by the government. They posited that the Nigerian government has enough resources to support education for all children at all levels.

The problem here would be corrupt practices, misplaced priorities, inequality, and poor policy choices. This was supported by others who saw education as a right, therefore, the government must not only endeavor to remove all bottlenecks to education but must also take steps to utilize the maximum of its available resources to progressively actualize the right of every citizen to education and other social and economic rights of citizens

In line with this, Hall (2013) observed, that funding public schools is one of the major functions of the government, agreeing with this assertion, automatically makes education funding completely off the parents of learners, however, it is obvious that what makes education and its programs attractive is the availability of funds to procure the needed materials and facilities essential for successful teaching and learning, even the human resources needs of the schools are also funded through the payment of salaries and allowances.

Education funding at all levels in Nigeria has indeed been more on the government, except at some levels of higher education. To this end, parents of learners have been enjoying free sponsorship of their children at school. It is obvious that what makes education and its programs attractive is the availability of funds to procure materials

and facilities essential for successful teaching and learning. Even human resources need funds for salaries and allowances. The issue is whether the government can single-handedly fund education to its full capacity. The answer is clearly “No”. Funding education in Nigeria should be a joint responsibility of the Government and private partners, the government should include the Federal, State, and Local Government areas of the various states in the country and private partners which include individuals of goodwill, private organizations, and other non-governmental organizations (NGOs). Agreeably, free education for all Nigerian citizens should be the function and responsibility of the government. However, the federal and state government budgets for education have recently been inadequate to manage all education programs and activities. Even the local government budget for education these days is laughable, politicians do not acknowledge the importance of education finance and the impact of under-financing on both education input and output. Nigerian politicians lacked interest in improving the quality of public schools, which made funding public education an illusion. Nigerian elite values and invests in private schools, all politicians in Nigeria educate their children and wards in private schools in Nigeria and other foreign nations. The public education budget, financial spending, and quality of public schools have been negatively impacted because the politicians who, make financial and other crucial education decisions no longer have a vested interest in public schooling in Nigeria.

Worse still, the underfunded Nigerian educational system has been bedeviled by the high cost of educational materials and facilities arising from inflation and corruption. It is important for administrators of the Nigerian educational system to always be prudent in managing scarce resources to improve the system.

Alternatively, Education funding in the face of Rising Inflation and Emerging Trends in 21st-century Nigeria should incorporate all available avenues through which funds, are raised for the education system and must be used to maintain the system to its full potential and capacity.

School administrators with the permission of both the federal and state governments can introduce minimal-level school fees and explore other avenues, as stated above, to support the government budget for education.

In line with this, Singleton, (2013) opined, that school fees are one of the major sources of education funding that could be used to offset administrative costs. Education stakeholders have, however, argued for free education and government funding for all educational needs. However, if borne by the government alone, the quality and standard of education input and output will be negatively impacted as the government alone can hardly fund all education needs in this 21st century.

In this era, it is also encouraged that graduates, old boys and girls associations of schools could also organize themselves and contribute funds to support their alma maters by providing some required material resources for the schools. Other sources of education funding in the 21st-century educational system could be from school handwork and the sale of school farm products, previously schools have made serious and huge funds from this before the clamor for free education.

In the face of this high rate of inflation, it is evidenced that the government alone cannot fund education, therefore, school administrators should support their school funds through the sales of school craft and farm products, which are derived from student handwork and agricultural activities of the schools.

The government can also enact policies and laws that support companies and private business owners within the school environment and communities as a matter of corporate social responsibility to contribute funds for the procurement of school facilities and equipment.

This will help school administrators, provide the necessary infrastructure for teaching and learning activities and improve the standard and quality of services rendered in Nigeria's 21st-century educational system. Learning environments in the twenty-first (21st) Century are envisioned as places where the learners are engaged in self-directed and cooperative learning activities. The physical environment should be planned to be routinely reorganized to make learning easy and better.

The quality of education depends on teachers' ability to perform their duties and the effective coordination of the school's physical environment. To this end, the efficiency of a school system in achieving its organizational objectives and goals depends on the effectiveness of the various physical environmental factors to which the system is subjected. The funds provided by the government and other sources cannot manage themselves unless somebody puts them to use, therefore, it is pertinent for the government to engage prudent school administrators to manage these funds, appropriating them accurately to avoid wastage and embezzlement in the successful actualization of educational aims and objectives.

Educational Administration

Educational Administration is a means of incorporating human and material resources for effective and efficient actualization of educational aims and objectives. Essentially, it encompasses all actions of planning, organizing, directing, coordinating, controlling, motivating, assessing, and, evaluating education programs and activities for better feedback in the educational system. Generally, education administration is directed towards goal fulfillment and achievement of the organization. Education administration is not placed in a vacuum; rather, it is placed on human activities, such as planning the activities, organizing them, executing the actions, evaluating inputs and outputs, and getting feedback for innovation and changes in the system. Therefore, education administration involves human actions in processing educational programs from start to finish. Education administration, as a social interaction that influences the utilization of human and material resources to achieve educational aims and objectives, is concerned with the following;

- Provision of quality education programs and activities for students at school.
- Improving the use of both human and material Resources.
- Protecting and maintaining Professional Ethics and development of academic and non-academic staff of the schools.
- Ensuring strict compliance with education policies and laws among the teachers and students.

- Providing necessary motivational programs for the teachers and students at school.
- Developing a feedback system to enable them to gather information for program modifications and improvement
- Maintaining and improving the school-community relationship within the school environment.
- Ensuring qualitative and well-standardized education programs.
- Ensuring adequate staff supervision
- Providing adequate, effective, and efficient financial decisions
- Ensuring standard curriculum design.
- Protecting the system from legal issues
- Protecting and managing the school facilities and equipment
- Providing functional school budgets etc.

The role of education administration in the face of Rising Inflation and Emerging Trends in 21st-century Nigeria should be more than the daily management of educational institutions in Nigeria, it should inspire and innovate good strategies, make adequate and necessary changes to improve and positively impact the teaching and learning processes of the school, and meet the trends of the advanced needs of the students, communities, and the nation at large. Educational administrators, whether as school principals or board chairpersons should play a leading role in guiding, directing, and ensuring the well-being of the education system assigned to them. They may also, not only supervise academic directions but also interact with all stakeholders, manage budgets, and serve as a vanguard for untroubled educational programs and activities. To this end, it is obvious that education administrators are not loners, they work with people who support in managing material resources provided for the school, not just managing resources but managing them without wastage. Emphatically, the role of education administration in adapting schools to the needs of learners and society is immeasurable.

Conclusion

Education as a purposeful endeavor that enhances an individual's values and knowledge, shaping the individual's and society's future through skills, norms, and values transferred by its process should not be treated with unseemly frivolity. Education funding should be taken seriously by all concerned parties. As noted, alternative means of raising funds for education should also be encouraged. The government alone can hardly sponsor all contemporary education needs that meet global best practices in education, mostly in the face of this rising inflation and emerging trends in education in Nigeria. Significantly, government bodies responsible for the employment of education administrators should do so without prejudice and eschew corrupt practices, nepotism, and favoritism in employment processes to produce trained, reliable, credible, and prudent education administrators who can adequately manage the scarce resources available to education without wastage and for better accountability. Strict adherence to these prepositions will make the future of education administration and funding despite rising inflation and emerging trends in 21st-century Nigeria easy and successful.

Suggestions

The following are here suggested.

1. Government budgets for education should be improved to meet contemporary educational needs that align with education best practices globally.
2. Alternative means of funding education should be encouraged through government policies.
3. Education administrators should place round pegs on a round hole without prejudice.
4. Consequence management should be applied to all circumstances in the Nigerian education system to restore administrative discipline and, reduce impunity and wastage in school finance management.
5. It is part of the corporate social responsibility of all corporate bodies in Nigeria to support education financially, therefore, the government should make this happen without delay through effective policies.
6. Corrupt education administrators should be sanctioned and consequently punished to reposition others who may wish to move to the same place.
7. Training and retraining of education administrators on global education improvement procedures and financial management should be encouraged by the government for effective and efficient school management and administration.

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